

THE TASKS OF CREATING AN INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY SPACE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL CULTURE

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Abstract: The social importance of the development of entrepreneurship culture, the creation of an innovative activity space in the development of entrepreneurship is considered in the article. Actual problems of development of entrepreneurial culture have been studied. In the development of society, the development of the state and society was assessed through the effectiveness of reforms related to trade relations, the effectiveness of reforms that have a positive effect on the improvement of business activities and business relations. As a result of the available opportunities and the reforms being implemented, scientific proposals and recommendations have been made for the development of entrepreneurship culture in our country.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, innovation, entrepreneurial culture, entrepreneurial person, economic efficiency, innovative space, business environment, profitability, market relations.

ЗАДАЧИ СОЗДАНИЯ ПРОСТРАНСТВА ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В РАЗВИТИИ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается социальная значимость развития культуры предпринимательства, создания пространства инновационной деятельности в развитии предпринимательства. Изучены актуальные проблемы развития предпринимательской культуры. В развитии общества развитие государства и общества оценивалось через эффективность реформ, связанных с торговыми отношениями, эффективность реформ, которые оказывают положительное влияние на улучшение деловой активности и деловых отношений. В результате имеющихся возможностей и реализуемых реформ были сделаны научные предложения и рекомендации по развитию культуры предпринимательства в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, инновации, предпринимательская культура, предпринимательская личность, экономическая эффективность, инновационное пространство, бизнес-среда, прибыльность, рыночные отношения.

INTRODUCTION

Creating a free and fair innovative activity environment in society is a necessary condition for creating a prosperous life. In order to ensure its progress in line with the spirit of the new era, it is necessary to manage the process of introducing innovations into social, economic, and cultural life, to create a favorable environment for the creation of innovation and its realization. In order to carry out such a task in the conditions of the transition to market relations, it is important to determine the priority directions of activities carried out in all aspects of life. The theoretical knowledge and best experience created in this field show that one of the main conditions for ensuring the viability of the product being developed in the market conditions is the establishment of innovative activities and its support in every way. After all, "freedom of entrepreneurial activity, ensuring the inviolability of private property will remain a priority direction in state policy from now on. It can be said without exaggeration that the consistent implementation of this constitutional rule determines the essence of all our work on the rapid development of a socially oriented market economy." [1.37] The practical aspects of the business attitude, which is an important part of the entrepreneurial culture, are of great importance in the effective activity of an

entrepreneur. All of them are, of course, important, but there is another unique aspect, which is the formed culture, the spiritual world of a business person.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

It can be achieved by creating a space for innovative activities in the development of entrepreneurial culture. It is not enough to connect the contents of business philosophy only with problem solving methods. From the philosophical and scientific approach to the issue, it is known that the philosophy of entrepreneurship includes not only the methods of solving the problems faced by entrepreneurs, but also the system of relations in which the values and ideals existing in the business world are determined during the activity of the entrepreneur. In particular, the philosophy of entrepreneurship covers the world of entrepreneurship as a whole. Western scientist W. James writes in his work "Pragmatism": "There are people - I am one of them - the most important, that is, practically important thing in a person is worldview. It is important for a housewife to know the income of a flatmate, but it is even more important to know his philosophy. I think that it is important for a general who is preparing to fight against the enemy to know the number of enemy soldiers, but even more important is to know the philosophy of the enemy.»[2.240] Therefore, the philosophy of business can be interpreted as a set of business methods, while it should be noted that it is not enough. In our opinion, to understand the essence of the philosophy of entrepreneurship, the method of perspectival approach related to determining the purpose of entrepreneurship is promising.

It is not without reason that the expression of innovative business, which expresses such creative activity, which is well-grounded in science and is carried out taking into account the changing conjuncture of market relations, is also in circulation. Creative activity in this field leads to the emergence of new unique product innovations in the system of market relations. The demand for such a product, which is a product of creative activity carried out at the same time as entrepreneurship, which embodies a very large intellectual potential, is becoming stronger and stronger. Therefore, the creation of such a product, the expansion of innovative activities aimed at introducing it to wide consumption is becoming a vital necessity.

One of the most important issues that arise in the creation and implementation of innovations is increasing the intellectual potential of innovative activities. In addition to the fundamental sciences that help to realize this goal, it is necessary to develop applied sciences that provide the opportunity to include scientific potential in the innovation process. The values of the entrepreneurial culture, which are formed and rising in the process of entrepreneurial activity, lead to the growing national values of our country and the deepening of market economy relations. [3.29] Therefore, the creation of a new organizational and legal space for entrepreneurial activity and the creation of a business environment constitute an important aspect of the development of society.

When creating an innovative activity space in the development of entrepreneurial culture, an entrepreneur makes decisions related to managing his business and increasing the material profit from his activities, the content of these decisions determines the purpose of the entrepreneur's activity. On the other hand, business is manifested as a specific form of human activity in society, the field of mutual relations between people. This process makes it possible to consider business in the following categories: people-goods-people. Therefore, when solving the issue of improving the scientific support of innovative activities, it is appropriate to take into account the widening of the use of small and medium-sized businesses in the conditions of the market economy, and the increasing participation of such systems in innovative activities. In order

to ensure the active participation of this industry in the production of new types of products and services, the problem of lack of intellectual resources appears. Such a problem arises due to limited funds, non-availability of a scientific-experimental base, difficulties in repair with scientific personnel in a small and medium-sized business enterprise or institution, which is the main consumer of innovations aimed at introducing new types of goods and services. Even if the people working in such enterprises demonstrate initiative and initiative and manage to eliminate the above-mentioned shortcomings, the scientific potential of innovative activity will be limited to the sphere of activity of this business entity.

It is natural for an enterprise or an institution operating in a competitive environment to try to preserve the income from the introduction of innovation, to keep the innovation it created as secret as possible. Therefore, it will not be enough to analyze business only in economic categories. Therefore, the process of honesty and healthy struggle to create a consumer creates an entrepreneurial environment and culture.

In developed countries, the state ensures the introduction of scientifically sound innovations into the field of entrepreneurship. In order to improve innovative activity, in most cases, innovative farms are established, which, in addition to the production of goods and services, also conduct scientific and research work on the creation of innovations.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The large-scale reforms carried out in our country are supported by our people. As a result of this, New Uzbekistan is known to the world as a free country that is developing, changing in every field, becoming full of strength, recognized by the people of the world. Thanks to democratic reforms, people with special knowledge and middle class who are able to carry out entrepreneurial activities have been formed in our country. In the early period of independence, entrepreneurial activity was stopped due to distrustful and cautious views of the economic and political reforms carried out by the state, lack of sufficient experience, knowledge, skills and special information complex, but now such difficulties have been overcome. Bureaucratic obstacles in the development of entrepreneurship and business, indifference of some local leaders to the work of businessmen were observed. In the period of deepening of market economy relations, although the state adopted laws aimed at supporting entrepreneurship as a new social stratum that is being formed, in some cases they were not followed, the complexity of obtaining and using bank loans in the conditions of inflation, the lack of entrepreneurs in society instead of a relatively negative attitude, the situation caused certain social difficulties. This was caused by the inculcation of ideological stereotypes against the essence of private property into people's minds during the period of repression, and at the same time, it was caused by shortcomings in the activities of businessmen. Such negative situations in the society, in turn, led to the formation of a certain negative attitude in the opinion of the public about the layer of entrepreneurs, their nature and purpose.

At the moment, it should be recognized that many Muslim countries are significantly behind developed countries in the field of science and technology. In order to effectively implement large-scale works aimed at the consistent development of socio-economic life based on a new approach within the framework of innovative activities, it is necessary to create a favorable environment for creative research and entrepreneurship aimed at the creation of innovation and its implementation. Such an environment is created in the integrated space of innovative activity. Specific mechanisms of activities aimed at supporting innovative activities have been developed

and are being developed in Uzbekistan. In fact, entrepreneurship developed on an innovative basis has a significant impact on the development of society.

Such a mechanism is based on bilateral financing, which provides for the attraction of investments from enterprises and institutions interested in the introduction of innovation, along with the allocation of funds from the state budget. The new mechanism also envisages the use of methods of returning funds allocated by the state, creating a number of benefits in the tax sector, and investing in new projects (injecting long-term capital into various sectors, socio-economic programs, innovative projects for the purpose of economic development).

In order for this mechanism to work effectively, it will be necessary to introduce innovative technologies in the banking system itself. In the process of making investments in innovative activities, the degree to which the planned innovation is based, the stability of the demand for it, the material-technical, intellectual, infrastructural resources of the innovative enterprise or institution, and the personnel with potential. It is necessary to rely on expert conclusions on many issues, such as the development of a marketing strategy, the existence of a clear action program, and the determination of the level of commercialization of an innovative product. Economic analysis aimed at determining the appropriateness of allocating funds for innovative activities and its profitability should be carried out at the following 3 levels:

1. Microeconomic analysis focused on assessing the availability of intellectual, material-technical, infrastructural resources and personnel of the enterprise or institution, which is considering the development of innovative technologies, the possibilities of commercialization and real profit of the created innovation;
2. Macroeconomic analysis focusing on the assessment of economic efficiency of the created innovative technology, goods or services in the enterprises and institutions that implement them directly;
3. Evaluation of the economic efficiency of the investment bank, which is achieved due to the activities aimed at providing funds to the innovative enterprise or institution, based on microeconomic analysis.

The above-mentioned points show that the financing of innovative activities is a creative process based on a large-scale economic analysis. That is why there is a need to use new technologies aimed at optimizing the activity in the banking system even in the implementation of this work at a high level. In addition to determining whether the new goods created for the purpose of wide consumption currently meet the accepted standards, it is also necessary to take into account the extent to which such products affect the formation of people's psyche and spirituality. Of course, it should be evaluated as a basic condition that the product of creative activity carried out for the welfare of society serves to ensure positive changes in the life of society and does not cause negative consequences.

Approached from this point of view, it is necessary to focus not only on the state bodies, but also on the broader society, as well as on the social importance of the establishment of innovative activity, expanding its scope and creating a space for integrated innovative activity. It can be concluded about In the conditions of market relations, along with the creation of innovative projects, there is a need to form economic structures that serve to deliver them to enterprises and institutions that implement them directly. It will be appropriate to use a new structure - business incubators, which is widely used in world economic practice, to fulfill such a large-scale task. In our country, the work being carried out within the framework of the Program for the creation and development of business incubators developed by the special institutions of the UN (UNDR,

UNIDO, YESSAR) and the State Property Committee on the basis of mutual cooperation is for the wide spread of innovative activity, training of innovative activity subjects. creates favorable conditions. [4.27] Creating conditions for the development of entrepreneurship in the international arena remains one of the urgent tasks of socio-economic development.

CONCLUSION

The expansion of the market of information products and services, which is a special form of entrepreneurship, which is developing rapidly in the present period, provides an opportunity for the direct production and service of innovative technologies.

In conclusion, socio-economic relations, new institutional structures, rational use of intellectual, material, technical and economic resources necessary for innovative activities, attracting scientific and technical personnel with high potential to innovation, market It serves to form a holistic innovative space with very convenient opportunities for creating innovative technologies that meet the requirements and putting them into practice.

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